

Flammability studies of multicomponent coir pith/nylon fabric/epoxy hybrid composites

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Abstract : Flammability of polymer composites represents how composite materials act under fire condition. Coir pith was treated with sodium hydroxide and followed by five different chemical treatments and used for filler in epoxy matrix. Hand layup technique was adopted for preparation of coir pith based epoxy composites. Chemically treated coir pith composites shows higher ignition time and lower rate of burning compare to untreated coir pith composites. Chemical treatment removes noncellulosic component in coir pith and improves filler matrix adhesion and it shows higher ignition time and lower rate of burning. Hybridization with nylon fabric further improves the flammability properties of composites.

Keywords : Polymer composites, coir pith, nylon fabric, epoxy composites, flammability.

Introduction

Advanced composite materials are good substitute for conventional building materials such as steel and concrete. Lignocellulosic reinforced composite materials possess various advantages such as cost effective, low weight, high corrosion resistance, low maintenance cost, high strength and also excellent mechanical properties. Lignocellulosic materials shows various advantages and also falls its own drawbacks like poor compatibility between polymer matrix and lignocellulosic fillers, i.e. agglomeration during composites processing, poor fire resistance, low moisture resistance, lesser durability, bounded processing temperature, distinction in cost and quality, and complicated in using manufacturing process¹⁻³.

Additionally the molecular structure of lignocellulosic material and polymer matrix are different and bonding between both phases are challenging. The presence of polar and hydroxyl groups in lignocellulosic materials make filler more hydrophilic in nature and results in lesser interfacial interaction between matrix and filler⁴⁻⁶. To enhance the efficiency of composites, lignocellulosic materials are treated with various chemicals. Chemical treatment removes noncellulosic material and waxy substance from natural filler and become more tender and effective coupling between polymer matrix.

Coconut husk consists of 70% coir pith, cork-like pith material considered to be non-fibrous tissues and 30% fibrous tissue. After the removal of fibrous part from coconut husk either by natural retting or mechanical process, the left out coir pith become a serious environmental pollutant⁷.

In our present investigation coir pith reinforced with epoxy resin and was hybridized with nylon fabric. The results showed that chemically treated and hybridized composites show better flammability compare to untreated ones.

Experimental

Materials :

Coir pith was collected from a local coir processing unit (Gudiyathum, Tamilnadu, India). Sodium hydroxide was purchased from Sigma-Aldrich, epoxy resin (LY556) and hardener (HY951) were purchased from Huntsman. Maaxil 402 mould release spray was purchased from Maax Lubrication.

Methods :

Chemical treatment :

Chemical treatment was carried out in two stages. The Raw coir pith (RCP) samples were first subjected to sodium hydroxide treatment followed by five different types of treatment.

Sodium hydroxide treatment (NA) :

Coir pith was soaked NaOH solution (5%) at room temperature for 1 h followed by washing with distilled water. Afterwards, the samples were oven dried at 70 °C for 2 h.

Dicumyl peroxide treatment (DCP) :

In peroxide treatment, the alkaline-treated coir pith was treated with dicumyl peroxide in acetone solution for about 30 min at 30 °C.

Sodium hypochlorite treatment (NAH) :

Sodium hydroxide treated coir pith were bleached by soaking in 5% NaOCl for 4 h at 30 °C and washed with deionized water until free from chemicals.

Acrylic acid treatment (AA) :

Sodium hydroxide treated coir pith were treated in 1% of acrylic acid (AA) solution at room temperature for 1 h, then washed with distilled water and dried in an oven for 72 h at 70 °C.

Acetic acid treatment (ACA) :

The alkaline treated coir pith was treated in glacial acetic acid for 1 h at 30 °C, it was decanted and soaked in acetic anhydride containing one drop of concentrated H₂SO₄ for 5 min.

Sulphuric acid treatment (SA) :

The alkaline-treated coir pith was treated with 64 weight % of sulphuric acid for 180 min at 45 °C.

Composites preparation :

A square steel plate mould with dimension of 450 × 450 mm assembled with top plate and base plate was used for the fabrication of composites. To help the complete removal of composites from the mould and to avoid sticking, a polyethylene sheets sprayed with mould release agent is layered on the top and base plate. Nylon fabric with a uniform coating of epoxy and hardener was spread on the polyethylene sheet. The pith/resin mixture (mixed in an internal mixer) is spread on this followed by another layer of resin coated nylon fabric. The samples were compression molded and cured over-night as shown. The resin hardener ratio is maintained at 10 : 1 in all formulations. The composites thus fabricated are denoted as given in Table 1.

Table 1. Material code and its abbreviations

Materials code	Materials abbreviations
BLANK	Epoxy resin
EN2L	Epoxy resin/nylon two layer
EN3L	Epoxy resin/nylon three layer
ERCP	Epoxy resin/raw coir pith
EDCP	Epoxy resin/dicumyl peroxide treated coir pith
EAA	Epoxy resin/acrylic acid treated coir pith
EACA	Epoxy resin/acetic acid treated coir pith
ENAH	Epoxy resin/sodium hypochlorite treated coir pith
ESA	Epoxy resin/sulphuric acid treated coir pith
ERCPN2L	Epoxy resin/raw coir pith/nylon two layer
EDCPN2L	Epoxy resin/dicumyl peroxide treated coir pith/nylon two layers
EAAN2L	Epoxy resin/acrylic acid treated coir pith/nylon two layers
EACAN2L	Epoxy resin/acetic acid treated coir pith/nylon two layers
ENAHN2L	Epoxy resin/sodium hypochlorite treated coir pith/nylon two layers
ESAN2L	Epoxy resin/sulphuric acid treated coir pith/nylon two layers
ERCPN3L	Epoxy resin/raw coir pith/nylon three layers
EDCPN3L	Epoxy resin/dicumyl peroxide treated coir pith/nylon three layers
EAAN3L	Epoxy resin/acrylic acid treated coir pith/nylon three layers
EACAN3L	Epoxy resin/acetic acid treated coir pith/nylon three layers
ENAHN3L	Epoxy resin/sodium hypochlorite treated coir pith/nylon three layers
ESAN3L	Epoxy resin/sulphuric acid treated coir pith/nylon three layers

Characterization :

Morphological analysis :

Scanning electron microscope (SEM) of Carl Ziess, EVO make was used to analyze the morphology of coir pith.

Flammability test :

Flammability of polymer composites were evaluated as mentioned in a previous report. The tests closely simulate the Federal Aviation Regulation, FAR 25.853 60s vertical burn test specification. 290 × 70 mm sized samples were suspended vertically using a clamp on a lab stand. An LPG Bunsen flame was applied to the leading edge of the bottom surface of composite. The time required to

catch fire is taken as ignition time. The flame time from the first mark (25 mm from the ignition end) until the second mark (100 mm from the ignition end) was measured to determine the linear burning rate (V) of the sample. The linear burning rate (V), was calculated in millimeters per second using the equation,

$$V = 60L/t \quad (1)$$

L = the burned length in millimeters, t = time in seconds^{8,9}.

Results and discussion

Morphology of coir pith :

Chemically treated coir pith effectively removes the waxy and noncellulosic material and also improves the surface roughness of coir pith. Chemical treatment activates the hydroxyl group of cellulose by breaks the hydrogen bond and coir pith become more hydrophilic. Fig. 1a shows the raw coir pith possess smooth and waxy layer. Chemically treated coir pith appeared rougher morphology it was further evidenced in Fig. 1b. The rougher surface of chemically treated coir pith shows superior mechanical bonding by an interlocking method⁸.

epoxy resin shown in Fig. 2. The incorporation of raw coir pith increase the ignition time. Because filler reinforcing in polymer matrix the geometrical configuration of polymer matrix will vary, so it possesses higher ignition time compare to blank resin. The chemically treated coir pith composites showed better ignition time than raw coir pith composites. This may be due the low percentage of lignin present in the composites systems due to the chemical treatment of coir pith. Thus with low lignin content the degradation begins at higher temperature.

The decreased flammability with natural fibres has been reported^{9,10}. So this results shows that coir pith act as better reinforcement in polymer matrix. The ignition time for coir pith/epoxy composites is found to be higher than the nylon/epoxy composite. The hybrid composite with treated coir pith showed maximum ignition time.

Rate of burning is a screening procedure for analysis of burning time of material in controlled heat flux. Pure epoxy resin composite shows higher rate of burning compare to raw coir pith reinforced composites. It reveals that pure epoxy resin is not suitable for flaming environment. Chemically treated coir pith composites shown lesser rate of burning compare to raw coir pith composites. In

Fig. 1. (a) Scanning electron microscope image of raw coir pith and (b) Scanning electron microscope image of sodium hydroxide treated coir pith.

Flammability :

Flammability of composite materials depends on the nature of composites, thermal conductivity, structure, nature of filler, density, humidity *etc.* The flammability of composites is expressed in terms of ignition time and rate of burning. Ignition time is the onset time taken by self-sustained flaming either on or near the material. The composites sample exhibit better ignition time than pure

order to improve fire resistance of composites, coir pith subjected to chemical (NaOH) treatment. It remove cellulose hydroxy group shown in Scheme 1. Treated coir pith composites shows higher flame resistance because treated coir pith disturb the normal pathway of pyrolysis to yield less flammable product. The hybrid samples with coir pith and nylon showed least rate of burning shown in Fig. 3.

Fig. 2. Ignition time of coir pith composites.

Fig. 3. Rate of burning of epoxy composites.

Conclusion

The present study showed that coir pith can act as reinforcing agents in epoxy matrix. Proper chemical treatment can reduce the ignition time further. In the present case the chemically treated coir pith/epoxy composites showed lower flammability compared to other composites. The introduction of nylon fabric also resulted in decreased flammability for composites.

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